

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT UNDER INDUSTRIALIZATION: AN OVERVIEW OF ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The article presents an overview of industrialization and its environmental consequences related to the transition from agrarian to industrial mode of production, definition and stages of industrialization, environmental awareness and education, modern trends in industrialization, industrial development, environmental and social aspects of industrialization, sustainable development under industrialization in Tajikistan and environmental aspects, waste management, prospects and challenges in Tajikistan and worldwide. Tajikistan faces significant climate change impacts that threaten the environment, urban infrastructure and the well-being of the population. Existing practices do not adequately support climate resilience and energy efficiency, which exacerbates environmental vulnerability.

Keywords: climate change, industrialization, environmental awareness and consequences, sustainable development, waste management.

Introduction

Tajikistan faces significant climate change impacts that threaten the environment, urban infrastructure and the well-being of the population [10]. Existing practices do not adequately support climate resilience and energy efficiency, which exacerbates environmental vulnerability. Industrialization is a key stage in the development of human society, associated with the transition from agrarian to industrial mode of production. This process began to develop actively from the end of the 18th century and had a significant impact on the economic, social and ecological state of the planet. In this article, we will consider the main aspects of industrialization and its environmental consequences [1,11,12].

Industrialization is a key stage in the economic development of any country, including Tajikistan. It con-

tributes to the creation of new jobs, higher living standards and improved infrastructure. However, rapid industrial growth is often accompanied by significant environmental problems that can negatively affect public health and the environment. Sustainable development under industrialization implies a balance between economic growth, social well-being and environmental protection [2,3,11].

According to the Agency for Statistics under the President of the Republic of Tajikistan, as of May 2024, there are 3560 industrial enterprises in the country, of which 326 units are in mining, 3064 units in processing, 72 units in supplying electricity, gas, steam and conditioned air and in water supply and waste treatment - 98 units (Fig. 1). Of the total, 1148 (32.2% of the total) are in Sughd province, 836 (23.5%) in Khatlon province, 786 (22.1%) in Dushanbe city, 681 (19.1%) in DRS and 109 (3.1%) in GBAO [1-3].

Fig. 1 – Number of industrial enterprises by data.stat.tj

Industrialization is the process of massive transition from manual labor and traditional production to mechanized and automated production. This process includes the introduction of new technologies, the development of factory production and increased urbanization. Raising environmental awareness and education plays an important role in solving environmental problems [8,9].

Awareness of problems and solutions helps society to take action to protect the environment. However, this process also comes with a number of challenges and environmental impacts. In the following decades,

especially after World War II, industrialization intensified. Large industrial complexes, such as the Tajik aluminum plant, were built and the mining industry developed [5,6].

Much of the output was sent to other republics of the Soviet Union [11]. Since the early 2000s, the Government of Tajikistan has made active efforts to stimulate industrial development (Fig.2). The main areas include modernization of existing enterprises, attraction of foreign investment and development of new industries.

Fig.2 - Share of industries in total volume of production in January-May 2024

Educational programs: Introduction of educational programs on ecology and sustainable development helps people to realize the importance of environmental protection and promote behavioral changes [11].

Environmental and social aspects of industrialization. Environmental consequences

As indicated by the Committee for Environmental Protection of the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan the industrialization of Tajikistan, as in many other countries, is accompanied by significant environmental impacts. Major problems include air and water pollution, destruction of ecosystems and waste accumulation.

Air pollution: Industrial enterprises, especially in the mining and metallurgical sectors, emit significant amounts of pollutants into the atmosphere. This leads to deterioration of air quality, especially in large cities and industrial areas.

Water pollution: Industrial wastewater discharges into rivers and lakes lead to deterioration of water quality and pollution of aquatic ecosystems. Chemicals and heavy metals are a particular threat, with toxic effects on aquatic organisms and humans.

Destruction of ecosystems: Expansion of industrial zones and development of mineral deposits lead to the destruction of natural ecosystems. This causes loss of biodiversity and ecological imbalance.

Accumulation of waste: Industrial enterprises produce a significant amount of solid and hazardous waste that requires specialized disposal. Insufficient opportunities for waste treatment and utilization lead to its accumulation in landfills and environmental pollution [2-10].

Waste management

Tajikistan's climate vulnerabilities and impacts reflect the broader challenges faced by nations heavily dependent on natural resources and exposed to extreme climatic variations. Effective waste management is an important aspect of sustainable development. In Tajikistan it is necessary to develop strategies for waste reduction, recycling and utilization. Key areas include:

- Introduction of separate waste collection systems: creation of infrastructure for separate collection of household and industrial waste will increase recycling and reduce landfilling.

- Development of the recycling industry.

Pic.1 - Linkages between CO₂ emissions and hydro energy production, technological progress, economic complexity, urbanization, and financial development by Farah Rana, Bilal Hussain, Abdelmohsen A. Nassani et al. [8].

1. Water Resources

Tajikistan's geography is dominated by mountainous terrain, which influences its climate and hydrological patterns. As climate change progresses, the variability in weather patterns increases the frequency and intensity of extreme events like droughts and heavy rainfall. This variability severely impacts water availability, which is critical given Tajikistan's reliance on hydroelectric power. Glacial melt, a significant source of freshwater, is also threatened by rising global temperatures, potentially reducing river flow during dry seasons. This reduced flow affects not only water availability for hydropower but also for irrigation and drinking water supplies.

2. Agriculture

Agriculture in Tajikistan is a vital sector, employing a large portion of the population and contributing significantly to the national economy. However, this sector is highly vulnerable to climate-induced changes. Drought conditions can lead to reduced water availability for irrigation, critical for the cultivation of crops such as cotton, fruits, and vegetables. On the other hand, unexpected temperature fluctuations can disrupt the growth cycles of these crops, potentially reducing yields and farmer incomes. Furthermore, increased temperatures and changing precipitation patterns can enhance the spread of pests and diseases, further threatening agricultural productivity.

3. Energy Production

Hydroelectric facilities generate a significant portion of Tajikistan's energy. However, the effectiveness of these facilities is directly tied to consistent water flows. Changes in precipitation and increased incidence of extreme weather events, such as droughts and floods, can lead to fluctuations in water levels, thus affecting

energy production. During droughts, reduced water flow can lead to energy shortages, while excessive rain can risk dam overflow and infrastructure damage. These fluctuations necessitate the development of more adaptive and resilient energy systems to ensure stability.

4. Heat Waves and Extreme Weather Impact on People's Health and Wellbeing

Increasing heat waves and extreme weather in Tajikistan, driven by climate change, have pronounced effects on the health and well-being of its population, particularly among vulnerable groups such as children and the elderly. Elevated temperatures lead to heat exhaustion, heatstroke, and dehydration, conditions that are particularly dangerous for the elderly who may have pre-existing health issues and less physiological resilience. In 2023, UNICEF reported that 1.7 million children in Tajikistan are exposed regularly to high frequency heatwaves. Even under the most conservative temperature increase scenarios of 1.7 degrees Celsius, exposure to high heatwave frequency is expected to affect all children in Tajikistan by 2050. As temperatures soar above 40 degrees Celsius across the country, UNICEF warns of the impact of heatwaves on children's health and well-being. Children and infants are particularly vulnerable to heat as their core temperatures rise significantly faster than adults, putting them at risk of heatstroke and other illnesses. These heat-related health threats are exacerbated in large cities, such as Dushanbe, by the urban heat island effect [10-11].

5. Economic Stability

The economic implications of climate vulnerabilities are significant. Disruptions in agriculture and energy production can lead to substantial economic losses. Moreover, the cost of repairing and mitigating

damages from natural disasters like landslides and floods requires substantial financial resources, which can strain the national budget. This economic strain can hinder development efforts, exacerbate poverty, and reduce the governments' ability to invest in necessary adaptations to climate change.

6. Food Security

Closely tied to both agricultural output and economic stability, food security in Tajikistan is highly sensitive to climate impacts. Disruptions in local food production can lead to increased food prices, reduced food availability, and higher import needs. In a country where many live close to the poverty line, increases in food prices can have severe implications for nutrition and health.

Fundamentals of sustainable development

Sustainable development is a concept that aims to meet the current needs of society without compromising future generations. The main components of sustainable development include:

1. Economic sustainability: ensuring economic growth and development, creating jobs and improving the standard of living of the population.
2. Social sustainability: ensuring social guarantees, access to education and health care, equity and justice.
3. Environmental sustainability: environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, pollution reduction and waste management.

Key areas include:

- Establishment of protected areas: development and implementation of programs to create national parks, reserves and other protected areas will help preserve biodiversity and protect unique ecosystems.
- Restoration of disturbed areas: carrying out activities on reforestation, reclamation of disturbed lands and restoration of ecosystems will help to restore lost natural resources.
- Education and awareness raising: raising environmental awareness of the population, conducting educational programs and information campaigns will help to draw attention to the problems of biodiversity and ecology.

Conclusion

Industrialization has led to the establishment of many industrial plants, which often emit significant amounts of heavy metals into the atmosphere and water bodies. The main sources of pollution are metallurgical plants, chemical industry, electronic industry, production and utilization of electronic devices. In the context of Tajikistan, with its unique ecological and climatic conditions, it is important to take into account local specificities and develop solutions adapted to specific conditions. Effective soil management and sustainable

development are key aspects for achieving ecological balance and ensuring a sustainable future.

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